

Malmö Jams Too 2017 - A Pilot Study on Development under Time Pressure

RISE SICS AB is a non-profit research institute for applied information and communication technology in Sweden. We have designed this short pilot survey to assess the feasibility of studying game jam participants to better understand time pressure in software development. After completing your project at GGJ17, we kindly ask you to answer our questions - each single answer means much to us in this stage of our research!

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Note that this survey is intended for GGJ17 participants that contributed to development of video games, i.e., games that are realized using software - board games, card games etc. are not in the scope of this work. The survey is intended for individual respondents - if you answer it as a team, please clarify this in the final questions.

The survey should take less than 10 minutes to complete. It consists of:

- i) six general background questions
- ii) four free-text answers (the challenging part!)
- iii) one large multiple-choice question
- iv) three quick concluding questions

Your answers are anonymous - they will be handled confidentially and used only for research purposes.

OBS! DET GÅR ALLDELES UTMÄRKT ATT BESVARA ENKÄTEN PÅ SVENSKA.

* Required

Background information

Brief background about you and your team.

How many game jams have you attended? (incl. GGJ17) *

Choose ▼

For how many years have you developed games? *

Choose ▼

How many jammers (incl. yourself) were part of your team? *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Did your team rely on an existing game engine during GGJ17 (e.g., Unity)? If yes, please provide its name.

Your answer _____

[Optional] Please enter the name of your team. (This helps us calculate the survey response rate, greatly increasing the validity of our study)

Your answer _____

Which of the following best describes your contribution to the team? *

- Programming
- Design
- Art
- Audio
- Other: _____

Which of the following best describes your non-jam role? *

- Student - related to game development
- Student - related to (non-game) software development
- Student - other subject
- Teacher - related to game development
- Teacher - related to software development
- Game developer
- Software developer
- Other job in industry
- Other: _____

Expectations on the game

In the beginning of a game jam, a team must establish a common understanding of the direction the project is going, i.e., a vision or a target picture. We refer to this as "expectations". In your own words, please provide brief answers to the two following questions:

How did your team initially capture expectations on the game, and how did you ensure that all team members shared the same understanding?

Your answer

Most likely the expectations evolved as the jam progressed. How did your team communicate changed expectations?

Your answer

Satisfaction assessment

Shared expectations is one aspect of development, another is to ensure that they have been met. We refer to this as "satisfaction assessment". In your own words, please provide brief answers to the two following questions:

How did your team assess whether the development progressed in line with the shared expectations on your game?

Your answer

In the final phase of GGJ17, how did your team assess whether your game satisfied the expectations?

Your answer

Development practices

Both the software and game development domains offer numerous best practices. To better understand effects of time pressure, we would like to understand which were used at GGJ17. Below we present a selected list of common practices, in random order - please select the practices your team applied (to some extent) during the jam. If you used any practices not listed, please provide them in the other field.

Which of the following practices did your team apply? Please select all that apply.

- Design patterns (general repeatable solutions to commonly occurring problem)
- Bug tracking (maintaining a centralized overview of reported issues and their status)
- Coding conventions (a set of guidelines for how to write code)
- Backlogs (a managed list of whatever must be done to deliver a viable product)
- Static code analysis (tools analyzing source code to identify deficiencies and vulnerabilities)
- Timeboxing (allocating a fixed time period to each planned activity)
- User stories (descriptions of what a user does or needs from the product)
- Refactoring (improving existing code without changing its behavior)
- Dedicated tester (one team member responsible for quality assurance)
- Version control (structured tracking and control over changes to source code)
- Scope management (defining what work is required to make sure only that work is done)
- Paper prototyping (creating rough drawings of interfaces to use as prototypes)
- Stand-up meetings (short meetings to escalate challenges and coordinate efforts)
- Pair programming (two programmers work together at one workstation)
- Code reviews (developers inspect each other's code)
- Iterative development (working product after each iteration enables continual evaluation)
- Continuous integration (merging all developers' contributions often)
- Automated testing (automatic execution of test cases to discover faults early)
- Minimum Viable Product (initial release with just those core features sufficient to deploy)
- Game design document (living document with vision and quality requirements)
- Exploratory testing (testing that emphasizes tester creativity and freedom)
- Waste elimination (avoiding any effort that does not add value to end user)
- Other: _____

Almost there... Concluding questions

Before submitting the survey, please answer the following questions.

How familiar are you with agile software development? *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not at all familiar	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely familiar				

How familiar are you with lean software development? *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not at all familiar	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely familiar				

How successful would you say your team was in GGJ17? *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not successful at all	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely successful				

Is there anything you would like to add before submitting the survey?

Your answer _____

SUBMIT

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